

THE HISTORY OF THE ORIGIN OF THE FORTEPIANO MUSICAL INSTRUMENT

*Navoi City Children's School of
Music and Art No. 1*

Umirova Xusnijaxon Musurmon qizi

Annotation: The history of the origin of the piano, the composers who contributed to its development are discussed.

Key words: music, method, art, taste, aesthetics, music culture, art , intelligence, listening to music, piano.

FORTEPIANO (ital. forte - strong and piano - slow) is a common name for grand pianos and pianos. 18-a. originally invented by B. Cristofori (Italy), J. Marius (France) and K. G. Schroeter (Germany). Later, the mechanism and form of the piano were developed by I. A. Stein, I. A. Streicher (Austria), A. Beckers (London), S. Erard (Paris) and others. improved by masters. The sound is produced by striking the strings with wooden mallets covered with felt. It differs from the harpsichord and clavichord in its dynamic range (ie, the ability to go from a strong peg to a piano level gradually) (hence the name). I. Haydn, W. A. Mozart, L. Beethoven, etc. wrote the first works for the piano. created Due to its wide technical and expressive possibilities, the piano has become the main soloist and accompaniment instrument in European polyphonic music.

Piano music in Uzbekistan 1920-30s. Starting with the Uzbek folk songs reworked by V. Uspensky, B. Nadezhdin, later by G. Mushel, H. Izomov, B. Giyenko, Sayfi Jalil, N. Zokirov, in recent years by D. Saidaminova, R. Abdullayev, A. Nabiyev, M. Otajonov, D. Omonullayeva and others. was enriched with miniatures, sonatas and concerts, multi-part series. A. Lisovsky, N. Yablonovsky, honored artists of Uzbekistan O. Yusupova, A. Sharipova, honored teacher of Uzbekistan T. Popovich, winner of international competitions E. Mirkosimova, A. Sultanov, U. Polvonov and

others contributed to the development of piano performance art in Uzbekistan. contributed.

The sound of the Museum's 1720 Cristofori differs considerably from the modern grand piano. Its range is narrower—54 rather than 88 keys—and its thinner strings and harder hammers give it a timbre closer to a harpsichord than a modern Steinway. Maffei commented that, because of its somewhat muted tone, Cristofori's piano was best suited for solos or to accompany a voice or single instrument, rather than for larger ensemble work. Indeed, a contemporary harpsichord was a louder and more brilliant instrument, but lacked the ability to respond to the strength of the player's touch, and so could achieve no significant gradations in dynamic expression. Like the piano, the clavichord ([1986.239](#)) is also capable of detailed gradations of loud and soft controlled by the player's touch, but this intimate stringed instrument is overall so soft that it can barely be heard a few feet away, and so is useless in ensembles or in concert.

Every year on November 8, Pianists Day is celebrated in the world. The holiday has no official status, but thanks to the Internet and music communities, it is becoming increasingly popular.

Variations on the justification of the date of Pianists Day can be found on social networks, but all of them are of a mythical nature.

Piano music, which appeared in the 18th century, quickly gained popularity, and in the second half of the century the instrument itself became widespread, which was a logical development of the harpsichord and clavichord.

Italian Bartolomeo Cristofori is the creator of the piano. The musical instrument, whose mechanism has undergone its own development and was mainly formed in the 18th century, now has two types of performance: grand piano and piano.

History has given the world bright, wonderful performers of piano music, each of them contributed to its development and improvement of the technique of

playing musical works. Each of them has a unique ability, a unique technique. Frederic Chopin, Ferenc Liszt, Pyotr Tchaikovsky, Sergei Rachmaninov, Arthur Rubinstein, Svyatoslav Richter, Josef Hoffmann, Vladimir Horowitz, Emil Gilels, Yevgeny Kisin and many other people cannot be forgotten.

As for the holiday, in Russia, Belarus, Ukraine, Israel, China and Austria, the tradition of organizing concerts dedicated to the Day of Pianists is gradually developing. The number of countries celebrating this holiday is increasing.

In conclusion, November 8 is gradually becoming a real professional holiday on an international scale, which can be celebrated not only by pianists, but also by fans of piano music, students in the field of piano playing, teachers and even those who created this unique musical instrument.

References

1. Sharipova G. "Music teaching methodology" T.: TDPU 2000.
2. Kadirov R. "Psychology of Music" T.: 2005.
3. Karimova D.A. "Music teaching technologies and design" T.: 2015.
4. Satvoldievna, U. D. (2021). Axiological Characteristics Of English, Uzbek And Russian Phraseological Units. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(06), 40-45.
5. Bakhtiyor, U. (2021). THE ROLE OF MUSIC IN HUMAN CULTURE AND IN SOCIAL LIFE.
6. Umurzakov, B. (2020). THE ROLE OF THE ART IN EDUCATION. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 29-2, pp. 4-5). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості= Голопристанский районный центр занятости.
7. Умурзаков, Б. Н. (2018). ФОЛЬКЛОР-ДРЕВНИЙ МУЗЫКАЛЬНЫЙ ЖАНР СРЕДНЕЙ АЗИИ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF THE PROBLEMS OF PHILISOPHY, PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY* (pp. 31-34).

8. Umurzakov, B. N., & Umurzakova, L. B. (2022). THE USE OF GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE MUSICAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 3(03), 13-16.
9. Nurmatova, M. M., & Ismoilova, D. R. (2021). BUILDING THE STRATEGIC COMPETENCE IN THE HETEROGENEOUS COMMUNICATION. *ВЕСТНИК МАГИСТРАТУРЫ*, 65.
10. Аббасова, Н. К. (2020). ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД В ОБУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА УЧАЩИХСЯ ОБЩЕОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛ. In *АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 49-53).
11. Aliyeva, N. (2021). ИЗОМОРФИЗМ АНГЛИЙСКИХ КОЛЛОКАЦИЙ И ФРАЗЕМ РУССКОГО И УЗБЕКСКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ С УЧЕТОМ ПЕРЕХОДНОСТИ ЗНАЧЕНИЯ. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 2(2).
12. ГАНИЕВ, Б., & Ганиева, М. С. (2019). Религиозно-исламские и духовные корни предпринимательской деятельности в Средней Азии. In *ИДЕАЛЫ И ЦЕННОСТИ ИСЛАМА В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОСТРАНСТВЕ XXI ВЕКА* (pp. 332-335).
13. Abbasova, N. K. (2020). O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA OLMOSHLARNING QIYOSIY TANLILI. In *МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 472-476).
14. Karimova, S. (2020). ҲОЗИРГИ ЗАМОН ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛЛАРИДА ТЕНГ БОҒЛАНГАН ҚЎШМА ГАПЛАРНИНГ ЛИНГВО–КОГНИТИВ АСОСЛАРИ. *Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики*, 1(1), 62-65.
15. Hayitova, M., & Mirzaahmedov, M. (2019). Basic problems in the teaching of English for kindergarten children. *Мировая наука*, (9), 21-24.